

MORPHOLOGY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CROSSLINKED PE/PE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Novel peroxide-crosslinked composite materials based on ultra high molecular weight polyethylene fibers were studied in comparison with their non-crosslinked homologues. Two material types were prepared, either by embedding the fibers in a low-density polyethylene matrix, or by compacting neat fibers. The resulting composites were analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry, focusing on the typical double-melting endotherm of the PE fibers, and by X-ray diffraction, concentrating on the characteristic weak 010 reflection of the triclinic phase in the fiber. Mechanical testing of unidirectional composites showed crosslinking to be highly advantageous, yielding significant property enhancement, e.g., increasing the flexural modulus from 28 to 33 GPa in the compacted fiber composite. The advantage results from the crosslinking mechanism, entailing only partial melting that is confined to the fiber skin, while retaining a significant degree of crystallinity in the fiber.

KEYWORDS: UHMWPE composites; PE fiber compacts; crosslinking; crystallinity

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INTRODUCTION

Polyethylene fiber-reinforced polyethylene (PE/PE) composites are currently utilized in a number of engineering applications including electronic [1], ballistic [2] and biomedical [3]. They are based on extended chain ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fibers embedded in different PE matrices, including HDPE, LDPE and LLDPE. Whereas the non-polar structure of polyethylene generally limits the chemical interaction at the fiber surface, in PE/PE composites, good adhesion between the fibers and the matrix is expected due to their mutual chemical compatibility. This is enhanced even further by the generation of a fiber/matrix transcristalline layer whose crystalline order and preferential orientation [4] produce significant property improvements in the fiber direction [5].

Crosslinking of polyethylene has been shown, in recent years, to be a significant property-improving factor, generating better wear resistance, fatigue life, thermal stability and mechanical properties. Typically, polyethylene is crosslinked by thermochemical reactions using free radical forming chemical agents, such as dicumyl peroxide (DCP). The crosslinking agent dissociates at an elevated temperature to produce free radicals, which transfer to the polymer chain and initiate crosslinking through the formation of interchain covalent bonding. The final properties of crosslinked polyethylene (XLPE) (e.g., thermal, mechanical and dielectric) are determined by the crosslinking conditions, namely, the concentration of the DCP and the reaction temperature [6,7]. Crosslinking can cause some adverse effects on polyethylene, such as contamination with peroxide residues and damage on the crystalline structure. Yet the advantages of crosslinking outnumber its disadvantages, particularly in the novel XLPE/PE composites in which an enhancement of the fiber/matrix bonding and interlaminar shear strength is expected. Such XLPE/PE composites were investigated recently for the first time for advanced circuit board applications [1], exhibiting a combination of significantly better mechanical properties and dielectric performance.

The preparation of the XLPE/PE composite requires heating to temperatures above the melting point of the fiber, while preventing its melting and maintaining its structural integrity. This can be carried out under a very high molding pressure, which raises the effective melting temperature

of the fiber [8] and delays the phase transition process [9]. It has also been shown that the lateral molding pressure is essential for retaining the extended chain structure of the fiber, preventing fiber relaxation and solid state re-crystallization by chain folding [10].

Another type of PE composites is processed of neat fibers only, whose partial melting at the surface provides the PE matrix. By employing a specific pressure-temperature sequence a hot compaction process can be carried out, wherein the fibers are fused together through their partial melting [11-13].

This investigation of crosslinked PE/PE composites is a feasibility study aimed at examining various crosslinking procedures through relating the resulting polymer morphology with the mechanical properties of the composite material. Two principally different composites are examined, which are either based on fiber-matrix systems or on hot compacted pure PE fibers. Most of the preliminary work was published recently in [14].

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS

A commercial UHMWPE fiber (Dyneema SK-75, DSM, The Netherlands) was used as the reinforcement. The fiber has a nominal tensile strength of 3.8 GPa and modulus of 118 GPa. Low-density polyethylene (LDPE) film, 0.015 mm thick, was utilized as received (Ganigar Plastics, Israel). Dicumyl peroxide (Lupersol 101, Atochem, Inc.) was used as crosslinked agent.

MATERIAL PREPARATION

Two different composite types were prepared, which were either based on PE fiber reinforced PE matrix or on compacted untreated PE fibers. For each type, both crosslinked and non-crosslinked composites were prepared.

Method 1 (XLPE/PE composites). In this method materials was pressed under 56 MPa at 135°C for 45 min (Carver laboratory press, model 2518), followed by water-cooling under pressure. The PE/PE molded prepregs were immersed in a cold solution of DCP in n-hexane (10% w/w) for 60 min, followed by drying in a fume-hood, to remove the hexane. In the final stage DCP treated prepregs were laid up in a mold and pressed for 45 minutes under 49 MPa at 160°C and then water cooled under pressure. Untreated prepregs, used to prepare non-crosslinked control samples, were pressed at 135°C. In all the experiments the fiber volume fraction was around 87%.

Method 2 (XLPE fiber compacts). In this method the fiber tow was pulled through a bath of the DCP solution and wound on a flat mandrel to the desired thickness, followed by pressing under 49 MPa, to obtain a unidirectional fiber compact. A non-crosslinked fiber compact was obtained by using an untreated fiber tow.

TESTING

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed by a Rigaku D-Max/B diffractometer with a Cu anode. Scanning was in the range of 10-41° at a wavelength of 1.54 Å.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was carried out by Mettler DSC-30, at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The weight of each sample was about 10 mg.

Flexural mechanical testing was performed in 3-point bending on a universal testing machine (Instron 4500), a loading rate of 5 mm/min and a loading span of 30mm. All the results were taken as the average value of five samples. The dimensions of the samples were: width 3.5-4.5 mm; thickness 2.0-3.0 mm; length 50 mm.

SEM- (Scanning Electron Microscopy). Etching was carried out with a permanganic reagent consisting of 1% w/v potassium permanganate in a mixture of 10 vol. concentrated sulfuric acid, 4 vol orthophosphoric acid (min 85%) and 1 vol. water. The etching time was 5 h. All specimens were sputter coated with gold and examined under a JSM 840 from Jeol SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MORPHOLOGICAL STUDY

Mainly orthorhombic structure with a small amorphous content was indicated by the X-ray diffraction data for the different materials. Figure 1 presents X-ray diffraction patterns of the original UHMWPE fibers, and Figure 2 presents those of the non-crosslinked PE/PE composite and PE fiber compact. The diffraction pattern of the fiber in Figure 1 shows the 110, 200, 210, 020 and 310 reflections of its orthorhombic structure [15] and a weak 010 reflection of the triclinic phase. The latter is typical of the UHMWPE fiber and has been assigned to a fiber surface morphology that is different from that of the fiber core [16]. The triclinic phase melts at 130°C and does not re-crystallize upon cooling [17]. The diffraction patterns of the composites, either of the PE/PE composite or of the PE fiber compact, differs from each other slightly in the relative intensities of the 200 reflection. Also, in comparison with the neat fiber they both show a significantly smaller 010 triclinic peak. In fact, the residual magnitude of this peak expresses the effect of the preparation procedure on the fiber skin, showing that whereas in the composite the fiber skin melts only partially, it does melt completely in the compacting process. Thus, in the PE fiber compact the 010 triclinic peak disappears completely. A more intense melting of the skin during the high pressure and temperature compacting operation could also explain the change in the relative intensity of the 200 reflection.

Figure 1. X-ray diffraction pattern of the neat UHMWPE-fiber.

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of: (a) non-crosslinked (PE/PE) composite; and (b) non-crosslinked PE fiber compact.

Figure 3 presents X-ray diffraction patterns of the crosslinked systems: the XLPE/PE composite and the XLPE fiber compact. The results are virtually identical to those of the corresponding non-crosslinked systems in Figure 2, underlying the fact that the disappearance of the triclinic phase, which was observed in the fibers, is primarily due to the melting of the fiber skin rather than crosslinking. In the crosslinked system too, the melting of the fiber skin is more intense in the PE fiber compact, expressed by the disappearance of the triclinic phase and by the change in the relative intensity of the 200 reflection. It is also interesting to note that there is no indication in the WAXS results of a hexagonal phase, observed in the DSC analysis (see below) and reported in literature [18, 19], as the orthorhombic phase is thermodynamically more stable below 150°C.

Figure 3. X-ray diffraction patterns of: (a) crosslinked (XLPE/PE) composite; and (b) crosslinked (XLPE) fiber compact.

Figure 4 presents the DSC results of some of the systems. The neat fiber exhibits the characteristic endothermic doublet (Figure 4 a). The first endotherm (at 148°C) is due to melting of the orthorhombic phase, followed by a partial solid phase transition from an orthorhombic to hexagonal structure, and a consecutive endotherm (at 153°C), which is due to melting of the hexagonal phase [19]. The triclinic phase, whose presence is confirmed by the X-ray diffraction analysis, disappears at 130°C [16, 17], where an endotherm should be observed. However, the small proportion of this phase makes it undetectable by the DSC analysis.

The melting behavior of the PE/PE composites (Figures 4 b, c) exhibits a more pronounced orthorhombic-hexagonal phase transition with an apparently more extensive hexagonal melting, which is shifted to a higher temperature (at 155°C) in the XLPE/PE composite (Figure 4 c). The melting endotherm of the LDPE matrix (expected at 110°C) is not detected by the DSC analysis because of the low volume fraction of the matrix and the low degree of crystallinity of LDPE (42%).

The DSC thermograms of the PE fiber and XLPE compact show a total absence of an orthorhombic-hexagonal phase transition in this system, exhibiting a complete orthorhombic melting peak at 145°C and 149°C, respectively (Figures 4d,e). This observation reaffirms the conclusion of the XRD study that a high temperature and pressure combination, applied in compacting (and crosslinking) the fibers, produces some changes in the crystalline structure of the fiber. This point is currently under further investigation by this group, to be reported in the future.

The overall degree of crystallinity of the fibers in the analyzed systems, (based on the melting enthalpies and canceling out the contribution of the matrix in the composite), is 77% and 74% in the PE/PE and XLPE/PE composites, respectively, and 79% in both the PE fiber and XLPE fiber compacts. The measured crystallinity of the neat fiber is 80%. It is seen that processing of the composites by either preparation procedure results in a decrease in the degree of crystallinity of the fiber. The crosslinking process does not seem to evoke an additional significant loss of crystallinity; hence, it is assigned to partial melting that is confined to the fiber skin. It is noted, for example, that the residual degree of crystallinity of the fiber is still significantly higher than that in HDPE. The high

residual degree of crystallinity of the fiber enables it to maintain its prime role as reinforcing phase in the composite.

Fig. 4 DSC traces of: (a) the neat UHMWPE fiber; (b) non-crosslinked (PE/PE) composite; (c) crosslinked (XLPE/PE) composite; (d) non-crosslinked PE fiber compact and (e) crosslinked (XLPE) fiber compact.

A comparison between non-crosslinked and crosslinked sample is presented in Figure 5. It shows the respective scanning electron micrographs of etched cross-sections. It is seen that although the fiber deformation under the compaction pressure is similar in the two materials, the crosslinking process eliminates a sharp separation between the fibers, generating a more continuous structure.

Figure 5. Etched cross-sections of samples prepared by hot compaction: (a) non-crosslinked (b) crosslinked.

FLEXURAL MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The mechanical testing destined to study the crosslinking effect included basic measurements of the ultimate strength and modulus. The results of the four material types are summarized in Table 1. It is apparent that the mechanical properties of the PE fiber compacts are higher than those of the respective PE/PE composites; for both material types, crosslinking results in property enhancements of the order of 20%. For example, the flexural modulus of the PE/PE composites increases from 18.4 GPa (in agreement with previously published results [2]) to 22.5 GPa.

Table 1. Flexural properties of crosslinked and non-crosslinked composites prepared by the two methods.

<u>Material</u>	<u>Stress at Yield (MPa)</u>	<u>Young Modulus (GPa)</u>
PE/PE composite	74	18.4
XLPE/PE composite	105	22.5
PE fiber compact	98	27.7
XLPE fiber compact	120	33.4

More importantly, while crosslinking is feasible only in the amorphous phase, the results of the fiber compacts suggest strongly that the peroxide treatment does actually generate significant crosslinking at the fiber surface, despite the high degree of crystallinity of the UHMWPE fiber. This observation is in agreement with a recent study on non-crosslinked PE compacts, which demonstrates that the extent of surface melting of the fibers can be controlled precisely by selecting specific temperature-pressure profile [20].

Based on the literature, bulk crosslinking of PE, occurring usually in the molten phase, incurs significant loss of crystallinity. Hence, its effect on the mechanical properties expresses two contradicting factors, namely, the formation of a three-dimensional network and the reduction in the degree of crystallinity. According to the literature, crosslinking of bulk UHMWPE (for example [21]) could result in significant property reduction of 6% and 40% in the tensile modulus and strength, respectively. And, only small property improvements were observed in solid state, radiation

crosslinked PE/PE composites [22]. In the PE composites and compacts of the present study, however, the combined effect of crosslinking at the fiber surface together with high residual crystallinity in the fiber generates high property improvements. Moreover, it is suggested that crosslinking at the fiber skin, either to the PE matrix or to adjacent fibers, intensifies this effect by enhancing the fiber/fiber or fiber/matrix interfacial bonding.

CONCLUSIONS

Whereas the X-ray diffraction and scanning calorimetry results do not provide clear evidence that crosslinking occurs at the fiber skin, the mechanical testing results do indeed. It is shown that through crosslinking, the mechanical properties of UHMWPE fiber based composites and compacts improve by an order of 20%.

Processing of the composites by either preparation procedure results in decreasing the degree of crystallinity of the fiber. The crosslinking process does not seem to evoke an additional loss of crystallinity; hence, the latter is assigned to partial melting that is confined to the fiber skin.

The source of the observed property improvement is the combined effect of crosslinking together with high residual degree of crystallinity in the fiber. Moreover, it is suggested that crosslinking at the fiber skin, either to the PE matrix or to adjacent fibers, intensifies this effect by enhancing the fiber/fiber or fiber/matrix interfacial bonding.

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